

Article

Climatological Trends and Effects of Aerosols and Clouds on Large Solar Parks: Application Examples in Benban (Egypt) and Al Dhafrah (UAE)

Harshal Dhake¹, Panagiotis Kosmopoulos^{2,*}, Antonis Mantakas², Yashwant Kashyap¹, Hesham El-Askary³ and Omar Elbadawy⁴

- ¹ Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, National Institute of Technology Karnataka, Mangalore 575025, India; harshaldhake.191ee212@nitk.edu.in (H.D.); yashwant.kashyap@nitk.edu.in (Y.K.)
- ² Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development, National Observatory of Athens (IERSD/NOA), 15236 Athens, Greece; sph1900119@uoa.gr
- ³ Schmid College of Science and Technology, Chapman University, Orange, CA 92866, USA; elaskary@chapman.edu
- ⁴ Centre for Environment & Development for the Arab Region & Europe (CEDARE), Heliopolis, Cairo 11737, Egypt; elbadawy@cedare.int
- * Correspondence: pkosmo@noa.gr

Abstract: Solar energy production is vastly affected by climatological factors. This study examines the impact of two primary climatological factors, aerosols and clouds, on solar energy production at two of the world's largest solar parks, Benban and Al Dhafrah Solar Parks, by using Earth observation data. Cloud microphysics were obtained from EUMETSAT, and aerosol data were obtained from the CAMS and assimilated with MODIS data for higher accuracy. The impact of both factors was analysed by computing their trends over the past 20 years. These climatological trends indicated the variations in the change in each of the factors and their resulting impact over the years. The trends were quantified into the actualised drop in energy production (Wh/m²/year) in order to obtain the impact of each factor. Aerosols displayed a falling trend of −17.78 Wh/m²/year for Benban and −44.88 Wh/m²/year for Al Dhafrah. Similarly, clouds also portrayed a largely falling trend for both stations, −36.29 Wh/m²/year (Benban) and −70.27 Wh/m²/year (Al Dhafrah). The aerosol and cloud trends were also observed on a monthly basis to study their seasonal variation. The trends were further translated into net increases/decreases in the energy produced and the resulting emissions released. The analysis was extended to quantify the economic impact of the trends. Owing to the falling aerosol and cloud trends, the annual production was foreseen to increase by nearly 1 GWh/year (Benban) and 1.65 GWh/year (Al Dhafrah). These increases in annual production estimated reductions in emission released of 705.2 tonne/year (Benban) and 1153.7 tonne/year (Al Dhafrah). Following these estimations, the projected revenue was foreseen to increase by 62,000 USD/year (Benban) and 100,000 USD/year (Al Dhafrah). Considering the geographical location of both stations, aerosols evidently imparted a larger impact compared with clouds. Severe dust storm events were also analysed at both stations to examine the worst-case scenario of aerosol impact. The results show that the realized losses during these events amounted to 2.86 GWh for Benban and 5.91 GWh for Al Dhafrah. Thus, this study showcases the benefits of Earth observation technology and offers key insights into climatological trends for solar energy planning purposes.

Citation: Dhake, H.; Kosmopoulos, P.; Mantakas, A.; Kashyap, Y.; El-Askary, H.; Elbadawy, O. Climatological Trends and Effects of Aerosols and Clouds on Large Solar Parks: Application Examples in Benban (Egypt) and Al Dhafrah (UAE). *Remote Sens.* **2024**, *16*, 4379. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs16234379>

Academic Editor: Manuel Antón

Received: 28 September 2024

Revised: 18 November 2024

Accepted: 21 November 2024

Published: 23 November 2024

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Keywords: solar energy production; climatological trends; Earth observations

1. Introduction

The ever-rising energy demand amidst climatic changes urges nations to tap energy from scalable, reliable and environmentally sustainable sources. Solar energy is increasingly

recognized as a critical component in the transition to a future of sustainable and clean energy. Consequently, solar parks (industrial-/large-scale installations of photovoltaic (PV) panels) are poised to become a principal component in power grids, especially in areas with favourable climatic (cloud-free) conditions combined with high solar irradiation averages at ground level.

Climatological factors (primarily aerosols and clouds) play a key role in the planning phase of any solar farm. These factors affect energy production at various scales, adversely affecting the production efficiency and economics of energy generation. This uncertainty in energy production makes it difficult to incorporate solar parks into the power grid. However, by studying such factors and quantifying their impact into comprehensible figures can help to develop load-balancing and production strategies that aid in the seamless integration of solar parks and minimise production and economic losses [1–3]. Additionally, these factors must be studied locally, and based on optimal climatic, terrestrial and local constraints, a location can be chosen [4]. Consequently, it becomes crucial to incorporate such analysis of these factors in the feasibility estimation of a project over the longer run.

This paper aims at bridging the connection between climatic factors and their direct and indirect impact on solar energy production. Countries like Egypt and the United Arab Emirates (UAE) have vast potential for solar energy production due to the climate, the landscape, and the high mean solar energy yield that can generate energy that suffices to meet substantial portions of the annual energy demand. Hence, in this paper, the Benban (Egypt) and Al Dhafrah (UAE) solar farms, two of the biggest worldwide photovoltaic power stations, are chosen for study. In this paper, the impact of two major climatological factors, aerosols (dust especially) and clouds, is studied and quantified in terms of energy lost, costs incurred and equivalent emissions released. These parameters are investigated by encompassing Earth observation data and modelling techniques. Nearly 20 years (2004–2024) of dust and cloud data for both solar farms were assimilated in order to study the long-term effect of these climatological factors. Over these 20 years, two instances of severe dust storms were also captured to analyse extreme cases (e.g., [5]). With such correlative analysis, this paper aims to help quantify the impact of climatic factors on solar farms and propose a generic framework applicable to other solar farms.

To quantify the impact of aerosols and clouds, first, the mechanisms and dynamics of both factors must be understood. Aerosols and clouds significantly influence the net solar irradiance reaching the ground. Some aerosols can scatter sunlight, reducing ground solar irradiance, while others, like black carbon, absorb solar energy, affecting atmospheric conditions. Additionally, aerosols serve as nuclei for cloud formation, leading to more reflective clouds that further diminish irradiance. Aerosols reduce the energy generation potential of solar panels by absorbing and scattering light, reducing the strength of the direct beam. Clouds themselves can either enhance or reduce solar irradiance depending on their type; thick, low clouds reflect much solar radiation, while high, thin clouds may allow more light through.

The stations considered in this paper, Al Dhafrah and Benban, lie in the dust belt of the Middle East and Arabian Peninsula with low cloud activity (compared with aerosols). Ref. [6] used AERONET data along with Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) data from MODIS (NASA) to investigate climatic changes, dust storms and the resulting solar radiation impact in the UAE. Dust storms typically largely affect solar radiation, and the resulting dust accumulation on PV panels further impacts solar energy production. Similarly, ref. [7,8] analysed seasonal variation in aerosols over the UAE during 2005–2015 and identified dominant aerosol and particle characterization. Coarse-mode aerosol particles dominate over the UAE during the dust season, while a high loading of fine-mode particles is mostly observed otherwise. The direct aerosol radiative forcing in the short-wave region at the top and bottom of the atmosphere was estimated in [9] with the use of the discrete ordinate radiative transfer method in conjunction with short-wave flux and spectral AOD measurements. The atmospheric aerosol forcing was found with higher values throughout the spring and summer seasons and suggested the importance of mineral dust aerosols in

solar dimming [10,11]. Similarly, studies like [12–14] estimated the impact of dust aerosols on surface solar radiation and solar energy in Egypt. Under extreme dust conditions, the AOD can exceed 3.5, and such reductions can cause financial losses that exceed the daily revenue values [12].

Both Benban and Al Dhafrah experience low cloud activity due to their arid location. However, cloud dynamics still affect solar radiation at a considerable scale. The Arabian Gulf shows a higher percentage of clouds during winter, while frequent convective clouds are noticed during summer [15]. Ref. [16] examines dust storms, dense haze and a smog-like phenomenon also known as the ‘black cloud’ and their impact on aerosol optical properties. Ref. [17] shows that clouds are capable of reducing outgoing long-wave flux by more than 30 W/m^2 and absorbed short-wave flux by 40 W/m^2 . The change in short-wave radiation due to clouds has a strong impact on the surface energy balance of the land, inducing a negative feedback for cloud radiation dynamics. Furthermore, studies like [18–20] present a physical linkage between solar activity and the dynamics of the troposphere and lower stratosphere. This linkage further enforces the effect of clouds on solar radiation due to radiation absorption and scattering.

Other studies, like [21–25], have helped to identify primary sources of aerosols and the net composition of aerosols at both locations. Figure 1 presents the average aerosol composition at both locations based on these studies and helps to identify that dust is the primary aerosol affecting solar radiation.

Figure 1. Average aerosol composition based on studies [21–25] for Benban, Egypt, and Al Dhafrah, UAE.

The primary aspect of this study pertains to quantifying the effect into comprehensible socio-economic parameters. In the literature, there have been several studies that have analysed and emphasised the importance of solar energy and photovoltaics and their impact on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, climatic changes and several other linked factors. Ref. [26] explores in detail the beneficial and adverse effects of utility-scale solar energy on the environment. Tapping solar energy comes with several hidden costs and effects which require additional regulations and standards to be put in place by the authorities for efficient and sustainable usage. Ref. [27] delves deeper into future outlooks and provides a critical overview of environmental impacts of PV systems. In fact, it provides several bases to nullify the notion that solar-energy is 100% eco-friendly and has no emissions (estimated at $14\text{--}73 \text{ g CO}_2/\text{kWh}$). Hence, it highlights future trends on design improvements for improved sustainability. Other studies have quantified this impact and have shown that a nearly 88% of CO_2 emission reduction by 2060 and a nearly 55% of GHG emission reduction by 2030 are projected for China and EU (and the UK), respectively [28,29]. Solar farms also impact the environment and have been proposed as significant means to fight climate change and curb GHG emissions [30,31].

Similarly, Germany offers benefits ranging from 19 to 93 EUR/tonne CO_{2eq} (with related assumptions and discounted cash flow analysis) [32]. Furthermore, ref. [33] advances a conceptual model together with quantitative methods to identify root causes and patterns in technological trends which lead to cost reduction and the mass commercialisation of technology. It applies this concept and models cost reduction mechanisms for PV systems for the coming years. This, together with suitable government policies, provides another financial incentive to private and public sectors to adapt to solar energy. Such a prospect in solar energy is already being realised with the 600 MW Al Shuaiba PV project in Saudi Arabia, tendered at a world-record-low bid of 0.0104 USD/kWh [34,35]. While there are several financial benefits to solar energy, there are concerns regarding technological advancements and installed capacity to achieve and maintain the Paris Agreement of 2015, as explained in [36].

Ref. [37] provides a very comprehensive overview on the impact of dust on the performance of PV panels and solar energy production systems. A clear understanding can be obtained about the behaviour of the system in the presence of dust and how the performance varies. Studies like [38–40] similarly provide a literature overview on the impact of climatic changes on renewable sources and highlight that the climatic changes and their effect on solar energy are projected to increase. Ref. [41] studied the performance of solar PV panels considering several environmental parameters (rainfall, dust, temperature, etc.). The performance dropped drastically as the environmental parameters increased and had a compounding effect. This also led to PV degradation in the long run. Ref. [42] performed a similar study for the region of the Indian subcontinent and forecasted the trends and climatic variables in two 30-year periods. The study found an anti-correlation between solar and wind variables and their impact on energy production. Works like [3,43–45] have reinforced the importance of the study of climatic factors by studying various factors like dust, water condensate, bird fouling, etc. Through these works, it was found that power dropped as low as 92.6% of capacity in the worst-case scenarios. While these studies were performed for individual to small-scale solar installations, the effects studied scale to large solar parks exorbitantly. Additionally, studies like [46,47] assessed the short-term impacts of environmental parameters, similar to the daily time-frame analysis performed in this study.

During the planning phase of any solar plant, investment costs and operation and maintenance costs are the two most discussed factors [48]. This fails to consider the long-term impact of climate around the installation and incurs hidden costs down the line. Furthermore, long-term studies like [49,50] provide a multi-year assessment of annual and seasonal trends in PV soiling. Ref. [49] also expounds on the effect of dust storms found on PV systems. Additionally, there are several case studies, like [51–54], which analysed the environmental impacts on solar energy production for specific areas and presented performance drops due to the variations in climatic conditions. Finally, detailed research studies, like [55–57], help to tie in the observed behaviour with the physical structure of PV cells reacting to climatic change.

After carefully understanding the existing literature on the climatic impact on solar energy production, it is evident that there is a lack of procedures that could help process Earth observation data and identify trends in climatological factors. Furthermore, the impact must be also quantified into socio-economic factors to be better understood by decision makers making long-term plans for solar installations.

The rest of the paper is broken into sections as follows: Section 2 expounds on the data utilised and the methodology adopted in this study. Section 3 presents detailed results of the procedure proposed. Final thoughts and conclusions are presented in Section 4.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1. Data

There are two primary facets of obtaining data for solar energy: Actual production values and simulated values. The data used in this study are based on the simulation

values for this period for both solar parks. All of these data are Earth observation (EO)-based, captured over a span of 20 years. The span of 20 years (2004–2024) was covered with monthly values of each of the input parameters. Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) methods (e.g., [58]) generally introduce additional uncertainties, since they provide day-ahead forecasts. For solar energy planning purposes, EO-based solutions highlight improved accuracy compared with NWP alternatives. This is the primary reason for choosing an EO-based approach over the NWP alternatives.

Similar to [59], in this study, the spatial and temporal resolutions of each data point were 3 km and 15 min, respectively. These resolutions allow for crisp details without overburdening the system with an extreme number of data. Additionally, no post-processing was applied to the input data, and raw data were used in the pipeline.

The cloud microphysics were sourced from the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT). Cloud microphysics refers to cloud parameters in terms of cloud type, cloud phase and cloud optical thickness, all retrieved from the official SAF NWC outputs from Meteosat Second Generation (METEOSAT-2) (explored in depth in [59]). Aerosol data were sourced from the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) assimilated with NASA's Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) data for improved precision of the results. By using these two climatological factors, simulated solar radiation and solar energy were obtained by using Solar Radiation and Meteorological Data Services (SoDa Pro) and Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS), respectively. While SoDa Pro and PVGIS are valuable tools for assessing solar energy potential, they come with limitations and uncertainties. SoDa Pro's accuracy depends on the quality of the input data and user parameters, which can lead to discrepancies in predictions. It may also struggle with localised environmental factors and short-term variations. PVGIS, while extensive in European coverage, may offer less reliable data in other regions and relies on satellite-derived information that can be affected by atmospheric conditions. Both tools may simplify complex processes and primarily provide historical data, which may not account for future changes [60,61]. However, these limitations were countered by using high-quality Earth observation input data aided by the Fast Radiative Transfer Model (FRTM) model (introduced in [59]) to ensure consistency in results with high precision. The FRTM model, in conjunction with Earth observation data, is able to generate high-resolution nowcasted surface solar radiation images, covering the entire globe with 5 geostationary satellites with 13.5 million pixels each. This helps to counter the above limitations of PVGIS and SoDa Pro.

The actual PV area is equally important in the estimation process (as explained in the following sections). Benban Solar Park is built on an area of 37.2 km² with a total solar panel surface of 26.86 km². Al Dhafrah Solar Park is built on an area of 21.18 km² with a total solar panel surface of 18.98 km². Figure 2 shows the satellite view of both solar parks.

It must be noted that the simulation values obtained for both solar parks were validated on a year-on-year basis, considering the energy conversion efficiency, losses and actual available PV area. These validations essentially verify the annualised energy production estimated from the simulations with the actual annualised energy production for each year. For example, for Benban Solar Park, the installed capacity/actual annualised energy production is close to 3.8 TWh per year. The simulation values for Benban Solar Park for the year 2023 resulted in an estimation of 3.70 TWh, thus validating the simulation values. Similarly, for Al Dhafrah Solar Park, the installed capacity is around 4.7 TWh per year, and the simulations for 2023 estimated 4.19 TWh.

Figure 2. Satellite view of solar parks (sourced from Google Earth): (a) Benban Solar Park, Egypt, and (b) Al Dhafrah Solar Park, United Arab Emirates.

2.2. Methodology

The aim of this study is to obtain climatological trends at solar parks and quantify their impact on the increase/decrease in energy production. This variation in production due to the climatic factors is translated into changes in the equivalent CO_2 emissions released and the revenue of the solar park.

It was crucial to harmonise the data from various sources (cloud microphysics, aerosol variations, real energy production data and in situ data assimilation) into a single pipeline for the model to simulate the exact physical interaction of radiation with clouds and aerosols and obtain their trends. The inputs to the Solar Nowcasting system are captured Earth observation data, cloud microphysics along with aerosol observations. The Solar Nowcasting system consists of the Fast Radiative Transfer Model (FRTM) [59] for nowcasting climatological patterns and thus solar irradiance. The nowcasted climatological patterns and resulting solar irradiance were correlated with geographical maps of Egypt and the UAE to obtain specific pixels and simulation values for both solar parks. The simulation values obtained from the FRTM are expressed in Wh/m^2 .

These pixel-specific simulated irradiance values give an accurate estimation of the solar irradiance observed at ground level and were further validated by using actual production data along with in situ measurements. Finally, to convert irradiance into expected energy output, the PVGIS calculator [60] was used to compute the percentage conversion loss for each solar park. PVGIS incorporates the following crucial factors to obtain the conversion efficiency of a system: angle of incidence, spectral effects, temperature, low irradiance, PV technology, PV mounting position, mechanical slope and azimuthal.

The simulated irradiance adjusted by the percentage conversion loss is a simulation value of one pixel in the entire image captured by the satellite image. Hence, the actual PV area needed to be assimilated during calculations in order to scale the simulations to the actual size of the solar parks and make suitable energy estimations. The simulation values were further scaled by using the actual available PV area of the solar park to obtain the simulated energy production value. This simulated energy production value is the final output of the system. Figure 3 depicts the entire process pipeline adopted for this study.

Figure 3. Process flowchart.

2.2.1. Aerosol and Cloud Effects

After the simulations with the FRTM, three classes of the simulation values obtained were particularly important in the course of this study:

- **Clean and Clear GHI (GHI_{00})**—Irradiance free of cloud and aerosol interactions. Essentially, this reading is equivalent to the top-of-the-atmosphere reading.
- **Clear Sky GHI (GHI_0)**—Irradiance free of cloud interactions only. The readings still incorporate aerosol interactions.
- **Actual GHI (GHI)**—Final irradiance reading inclusive of cloud and aerosol interactions. Essentially, this reading is equivalent to surface solar irradiance. For the purposes of this study, this reading is considered implicit of the water vapour effect, as solar radiation has light sensitivity to this effect [62].

Aerosol effect and cloud effect form the basis of analysis for the entirety of this study. Using the above three values, the aerosol effect and the cloud effect can be obtained. Essentially, both effects are defined as follows:

- **Aerosol effect:** The aerosol effect refers to the loss in radiation due aerosol interactions (scattering and absorption) in the atmosphere.
- **Cloud effect:** The cloud effect refers to the loss in radiation due to cloud interactions (reflection, absorption and diffraction) in the atmosphere.

Naturally, following their definitions, they are computed as

$$\text{Aerosol Effect} = GHI_{00} - GHI_0$$

$$\text{Cloud Effect} = GHI_0 - GHI.$$

2.2.2. Climatological Trends

Climatological trends refers to the linear trends obtained for aerosol and cloud effects over the course of a time period. In this study, the data conformed to 15 min temporal resolution within a 20-year-time period. The linear trends in aerosol and cloud effects showcase the natural shift in climate (owing to climatic changes, industrial changes, etc.) and the atmospheric properties over the time period. A rising (positive) trend value for any of the effects would imply that that particular climatological factor is increasing over the years and its effect is increasingly imposing adverse effects on energy production. A falling

(negative) trend value would indicate otherwise. Having a sense of these trends for any particular site under consideration allows decision makers to have insights into the climatic challenges the solar park may face.

Hence, after obtaining the aerosol and cloud effects, the linear trends for both effects were computed over the 20 years. The data-series of each effect for each station for each month was fitted by using a linear regression to obtain the slope of the best-fitting line [63]. This slope is essentially the trend of the effect and is represented by Wh/m²/year.

2.2.3. Quantification of Impact in Terms of Energy, Emissions and Revenue

The aerosol and cloud effects were further processed into energy values in order to quantify the impact of both climatological factors in terms of energy. The key energy values were used for the analysis of the energy impact: $E_{lost,aerosols}$, $E_{lost,clouds}$ and E_{net} .

$E_{lost,aerosols}$ denotes the energy lost due to aerosol interactions and is computed as follows:

$$E_{lost,aerosols} = (\mathbf{GHI}_{00} - \mathbf{GHI}_0) \times (1 - \eta) \times Area_{actual}$$

$E_{lost,clouds}$ denotes the energy lost due to cloud interactions and is computed as follows:

$$E_{lost,clouds} = (\mathbf{GHI}_0 - \mathbf{GHI}) \times (1 - \eta) \times Area_{actual}$$

E_{net} denotes the energy lost after considering aerosol and cloud interactions and is computed as follows:

$$E_{lost,net} = \mathbf{GHI} \times (1 - \eta) \times Area_{actual}$$

Note that η here refers to the percentage conversion loss obtained with PVGIS.

The linear trend of E_{net} was computed on a monthly basis to quantify the impact of both climatological effects on the final energy production. The E_{net} trend obtained (in Wh/m²/year) was scaled to the actual PV area available at both parks to obtain the production energy trend (in MWh/year). This energy trend value helps to quantify the net rise or fall observed in solar energy production owing to changing climatic factors. Since each of the trends so far were considered on a monthly basis, a cumulative annual trend was computed by taking the sum of trends for all months.

The energy trend was also processed to compute the equivalent CO₂ emissions. The energy-to-emission conversion factor (in kg/kWh) was computed with the help of the GHG Equivalencies Calculator [64]. It should be noted that the equivalent emissions released refer to the emissions released by alternative traditional energy sources required to replace the energy losses in solar energy production for a constant power supply in the power grid. This helps in identifying the indirect climatic impact of clouds and aerosols from the perspective of energy generation.

Both solar parks are geared towards supplying electricity to urban power grids. The cost of production and the tariff of power sold are known values for each solar park, and this difference between the prices per kWh was used to compute the potential earnings lost due to the effects of clouds and aerosols. Hence, the trend in revenue (in USD/year) was obtained.

2.2.4. Analysing Extreme Dust Events

As seen in Figure 1, dust is the primary component of aerosols at both solar parks. Additionally, surveys and studies like [21,23] have shown that dust dominates contributions to AOD, contributing at least 48% (and more) in both regions. Owing to this fact, the analysis of extreme cases of aerosol effect must be studied to grasp the changes in worst-case scenarios.

Extreme dust storm events were recorded in the Benban region in March 2024 and in the Al Dhafrah region in May 2022. Both these events were studied by using the above procedure to identify the impact in cases with extreme aerosol interactions. The dust events occurred in a period of 2–3 days. Additionally, for comparative purposes, a week-long period is adequate in order to see the solar energy production levels under normal

conditions (just before and after the dust event). This technique also provides insights into the localised average and points of extrema for the entire event. In addition to the procedure presented in the previous section, drops in energy produced and resulting production losses, earnings losses and equivalent emissions losses were identified.

For both these cases, the distribution of the Aerosol Modification Factor (AMF) and Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) was computed. This analysis was used to understand the behaviour of aerosols in the atmosphere. Furthermore, the AOD was correlated with the energy produced to observe the direct impact of AOD on energy production.

AMF and AOD collectively offer a comprehensive understanding of how aerosols interact with solar radiation and influence atmospheric processes. They are defined as follows:

$$\text{AMF} = \frac{\text{GHI}_0}{\text{GHI}_{00}}$$

$$\text{AOD} = -1 \times \ln \text{AMF}$$

Thus, from the above relations, it can be established that the AMF and AOD are inversely correlated. As the AMF decreases, AOD increases, implying that aerosols are imparting greater reduction effects on solar radiation.

3. Results

3.1. Aerosol and Cloud Effects

As defined in above sections, the primary metrics to be studied in this paper are the aerosol and cloud effects. Figure 4 plots the aerosol and cloud effects for both stations. Owing to the monthly basis of the readings, the values in the plot are available as averages of the effect across the entire month. These averages adequately portray the underlying effect and highlight its nature on a larger time scale, whilst the 15 min temporal scale allows one to zoom in and closely examine the historical data if required. The aerosol and cloud effects, naturally, are not constant throughout the month and are dependent on the ongoing season. To capture their variation throughout the month, Figure 5 shows the monthly variability of both climatological effects.

It is evident from the graphs that the aerosol effect is much more prominent than the cloud effect at both solar parks. This naturally conforms to the locations of the solar parks. Additionally, it was observed that Al Dhafrah, UAE, faced more penalties in terms of both aerosol and cloud effects. While both the UAE and Egypt are affected by dust storms, the UAE tends to face more frequent and severe dust events due to its geographical features, arid climate, and larger expanses of desert. The UAE is located in a more arid desert environment, with vast expanses of desert and sandy terrain, making it more susceptible to dust storms. In contrast, Egypt has the Nile River, which provides some vegetation and moisture, slightly mitigating dust conditions. Furthermore, dust storms in the UAE can be quite severe due to the vast open areas without vegetation that can stabilise the soil.

Upon closer examination, the effects obtained in this study closely conform to the natural climatic cycle and seasonal variations found at both locations. The following analysis of the aerosol effect was performed based on the results obtained and local meteorological observations:

1. Dust activity and storms increase and reach the apex during the spring (March–May) and summer (June–August) seasons for both the UAE and Egypt. Consequently, the aerosol effect is also found to be increasing and experiencing peak “losses” during these months.
2. The autumn season (September–November) experiences diminishing yet moderate amounts of dust activity at both locations, which is reflected in the falling bars in Figure 5.
3. The winter season (December–February) experiences the least amount of dust activity and hence the lowest variation values in the graphs.

Figure 4. Climatological effects on energy produced at both solar parks. (a) Aerosol effect at Benban, (b) cloud effect at Benban, (c) aerosol effect at Al Dhafrah and (d) cloud effect at Al Dhafrah.

Figure 5. Monthly variability in climatological effects over 20 years. (a) Benban Solar Park. (b) Al Dhafrah Solar Park.

In parallel to this, the cloud effect shows somewhat opposite behaviour to the aerosol Effect:

1. The higher temperatures, low relative humidity and clearer skies during the spring and summer (March–August) seasons facilitate lower cloud activity, resulting in the dips in monthly variation in the cloud effect at both locations.
2. On the contrary, the relatively lower temperatures during the autumn and winter seasons (September–February) increase the chances of low stratus cloud formation and occasional fog. Additionally, the Nile basin in Egypt boosts cloud formation in the

coastal region during this period. Benban, however, being situated more inland, does not experience the same cloud activity. This is also reflected in the graphs obtained.

3.2. Climatological Effects Trend Analysis

After obtaining the aerosol and cloud effects in the previous section, in this section, the trend analysis of both effects is presented. The trends were computed by using the simple linear regression, which is a popular method to quantify the trends of time series [63]. These trends represent the general notion of shift in the variation. Figure 6 presents the trend values obtained for both effects at both locations. These trend values are in fact the slopes of the trend lines obtained for the data series of a particular location during a particular month over the span of 20 years. It was observed that aerosols displayed a falling annual trend of $-17.78 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{year}$ for Benban and $-44.88 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{year}$ for Al Dhafrah. The clouds also experienced a largely falling trend for both stations, $-36.29 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{year}$ for Benban and $-70.27 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{year}$ for Al Dhafrah.

Figure 6. Monthly trend values in climatological effects over 20 years. (a) Benban Solar Park. (b) Al Dhafrah Solar Park.

A positive trend value implies that the effect is seeing an increasing range of values and hence that its impact is growing more prominent over the years. The converse can be said about a negative trend value. Trend values closer to 0 mark the effect as being relatively stable over the years.

3.3. Quantification of Impact on Energy, Emissions and Revenue

Calculating the energy production values after the consideration of both effects (E_{net}) helps to quantify the effects into comprehensible and simpler measurable terms. A trend analysis of E_{net} revealed the general notion of change in the production values purely due to change in the underlying climatological effects. Figure 7 presents this trend analysis of E_{net} . While the Benban region experiences a trend ranging between $-25 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{year}$

and 50 Wh/m²/year, Al Dhafrah experiences a diverse range of −90 Wh/m²/year to 130 Wh/m²/year. By summing all the trend values, we obtained an annual trend in energy production of 50.36 Wh/m²/year for Benban and a whopping 118.7 Wh/m²/year for Al Dhafrah.

Figure 7. Monthly trend in energy produced per square meter per year for each month.

Table 1 translates these trends into actual energy production, equivalent emissions and revenue trends. The table uses the following values of parameters for the computation:

$$\eta_{\text{Benban}} = 25.44\%$$

$$\eta_{\text{AlDhafrah}} = 26.77\%$$

$$Area_{\text{actual,Benban}} = 26868654.32 \text{ m}^2$$

$$Area_{\text{actual,AlDhafrah}} = 18988389.12 \text{ m}^2$$

η was obtained by using the PVGIS calculator as mentioned in the earlier sections, and the actual PV area was obtained from the technical specifications publicly available on the solar parks' websites.

Table 1. Socio-economic parameter trend analysis for both solar parks using the trends in Figure 7.

Site	Month	Energy Production ¹	Emissions ²	Revenue ³
Benban	January	500.83	350.08	31,251.90
	February	212.35	148.43	13,250.81
	March	−286.48	−200.25	−17,876.09
	April	897.49	627.35	56,003.40
	May	−94.16	−65.82	−5875.36
	June	42.67	29.83	2662.66
	July	−20.43	−14.28	−1275.08
	August	−274.46	−191.84	−17,126.04
	September	−460.77	−322.07	−28,751.75
	October	194.32	135.83	12,125.74
	November	87.14	60.91	5437.83
	December	210.35	147.03	13,125.80

Table 1. Cont.

Site	Month	Energy Production ¹	Emissions ²	Revenue ³
Al Dhafrah	January	1369.66	957.39	85,466.91
	February	−315.65	−220.64	−19,696.43
	March	−891.32	−623.03	−55,618.56
	April	860.73	601.65	53,709.66
	May	−444.97	−311.03	−27,765.90
	June	472.78	330.47	29,501.27
	July	−1186.11	−829.09	−74,013.47
	August	824.58	576.38	51,453.68
	September	−169.64	−118.58	−10,585.75
	October	−285.06	−199.25	−17,787.53
	November	−141.83	−99.14	−8850.38
	December	1557.38	1088.61	97,180.64

¹ Unit—MWh/year. ² Unit—tonnes/year. ³ Unit—USD/year.

The revenue of a solar park is computed by using the tariff rates employed and the costs incurred for production. The changes in energy are linked to its USD trade value decided between the generation plants and the power grid consumers. For the case of Benban Solar Park, the production cost was estimated to be 0.081 USD/kWh, sold at 0.1434 USD/kWh [65] under a 25-year contract signed with the MERE. Thus, the solar park makes 0.0624 USD per kWh of solar power tapped. Similarly, Al Dhafrah Solar Park generates a revenue of 0.0132 USD per kWh of solar power delivered.

The trends can be comprehended in the following way: a positive trend value of 25 Wh/m²/year results in an increase in energy production of 500.83 MWh/year. This increase in energy production results in an additional revenue of 31,251.90 USD/year and saves 350.08 tonnes/year of equivalent CO₂ emissions (case of January at Benban).

Having high positive values hints at the climatic and economic feasibility of solar parks in the longer run. Summing the trend values from the table gives the annual trend values for each metric. Owing to the falling aerosol and cloud trends, the annual production was foreseen to increase by nearly 1.008 GWh/year in the case of Benban and 1.65 GWh/year in the case of Al Dhafrah. This increase in annual production translates into a reduction in emission released of 705.2 tonnes/year by Benban Solar Park and 1153.7 tonnes/year by Al Dhafrah Solar Park. The projected revenue was foreseen to increase by 62,953.83 USD/year for Benban and 102,994.13 USD/year (Al Dhafrah).

During the decision-making process for such large solar plants, decision makers consider certain parameters to assess the feasibility of the project. While these parameters do not form a completely exhaustive list involved in decision making, their accurate estimation helps to form a preliminary analysis of the project. The factors are energy demand and market, environmental impact, and geographical and climatic factors. Such climatological analysis can be easily extended for other future projects to assess the climatic impact on feasibility and the resulting indirect impact on socio-economic factors and aid the decision-making process.

3.4. Dust Event Analysis

Studying extreme cases is important for achieving a complete understanding of the estimation model. In the previous section, a monthly time frame was used along with trend analysis in the estimation model presented in Figure 3. However, a finer time frame is required for estimating impact in worst-case scenarios.

The regions where these two solar parks are located are often affected by events of great dust activity such as dust storms and winds. In this section, two such extreme events of dust storms in the Benban region in March 2024 and in the Al Dhafrah region in May 2022 are analysed.

The first step in performing the analysis is capturing the required data from Earth observations, CAMS and SoDa Pro along with in situ assimilation. Continual monitoring

from in situ measurements produces a series of irradiance readings that present the pattern followed in the day. Figure 8 shows the GHI readings throughout the observation time period for each day.

Figure 8. GHI readings during dust events at (a) Benban Solar Park (b) Al Dhafrah Solar Park.

The dust storm was on 17th and 18th March 2024, and the solar park experienced maximum interference due to high amounts of dust in the atmosphere and on PV plates. The time frame of observation for Benban, therefore, was taken from 15th to 20th March 2024. Similarly, for Al Dhafrah, the dust storm was on 25th to 29th May 2022, and the time frame of observation chosen was from 22th to 30th May 2022.

The Clear Sky GHI readings (shown as red lines in Figure 8) include the aerosol effect; thus, they are lower in magnitude on the days of the dust storms due to dust interference. Figure 9 shows this dust effect (i.e., the aerosol effect) in Wh/m^2 . The days of the storms experienced the maximum drop in potential. Other days experienced “normal” dust interference. Furthermore, the maximum points in the plot are skewed on storm days, indicating the varying intensity of the storm throughout the day.

Figure 9. Dust effect during dust storms at (a) Benban solar park (b) Al Dhafrah solar park.

This analysis is supported by the AMF and AOD readings in the same time frame. Both parameters collectively help in explaining the interaction of solar irradiation with aerosols and the reduction in radiation by the time it reaches the Earth’s surface. Figure 10 shows the readings obtained for the AMF throughout the observation period for both locations. It can be observed that during peak dust events, the AMF dipped, signifying maximum aerosol interaction and hence lower irradiance at the surface level.

Figure 10. Aerosol Modification Factor readings during dust storms at (a) Benban solar park (b) Al Dhafrah solar park

The AOD values (taken as the maximum of the day) are plotted along with the actual energy produced in the day in Figure 11 to understand the correlation between the two metrics and how AOD explains the aerosol effect. An inverse correlation was identified between AOD and actual energy production. This suggests that as the AOD increases, the aerosol effect increases; thus, the energy production takes a hit, and vice versa. However, it should be noted that the correlation is not always direct, and deviations (owing to other aerosol components and factors) tend to take place in the correlation.

Following the analysis heuristics established until now, the GHI readings were translated into equivalent losses in energy production. These losses in energy production were further processed to obtain the resulting emissions released and earnings lost. Performing such retrospective analysis not only helps to identify the impact of the dust storms but also helps to prepare for any future events.

Table 2 shows the irradiance simulation values at the ground level along with the loss in irradiance incurred due to the dust effect each day.

Tables 3 and 4 show the estimates obtained for both solar parks. The production values were computed for surface solar irradiance obtained via simulations with and without the aerosol effect. For production values without aerosol effect, the net surface irradiance was simply summed with the irradiance lost due to aerosol. The net losses incurred in energy produced during the dust storms were nearly 2.86 GWh for Benban and 5.91 GWh for Al Dhafrah. The values of net revenue lost due to these losses were USD 178,302.64 for Benban Solar Park and USD 78,000 for Al Dhafrah Solar Park. These losses in energy production resulted in 1997.3 tonnes of equivalent CO₂ emissions released for Benban and 4130.6 tonnes for Al Dhafrah. Hence, by using this analysis of dust events, the extreme-case impact of the aerosol effect (and climatological effects in general) can be obtained.

Figure 11. Aerosol Optical Depth readings against actual energy production values during dust storms at (a) Benban solar park (b) Al Dhafrah solar park.

Table 2. Solar Irradiance simulations during dust storm events.

Site	Date	Net Surface Solar Irradiance ¹	Irradiance Lost Due to Aerosol ¹
Benban Solar Park	15/03/2024	376.090	185.376
	16/03/2024	237.752	171.477
	17/03/2024	417.883	220.136
	18/03/2024	153.477	272.234
	19/03/2024	556.213	174.831
	20/03/2024	566.900	167.789
Al Dhafrah Solar Park	22/05/2022	919.675	311.397
	23/05/2022	938.428	293.507
	24/05/2022	903.102	329.655
	25/05/2022	840.822	392.710
	26/05/2022	806.911	427.356
	27/05/2022	842.330	392.635
	28/05/2022	863.683	371.933
	29/05/2022	842.773	393.461
	30/05/2022	928.869	307.937

¹ Unit—Wh/m².

There have been several previous studies analysing the impact of climatic changes on solar energy production. However, a majority of these studies have dealt with the direct energy production impact and (or) levelized cost of solar electricity (LCOE). Ref. [66] showed the economic consequences of reversible and irreversible PV degradation due to the harsh climate in Iraq, suggesting a near 30% increase in LCOE due to climatic changes and an additional 4.4% due to soiling. The relation between the degradation of types of PV technologies due to climatic changes and the resulting changes in LCOE was studied in [67], and a model integrating local climate into levelised cost of photovoltaic technology

was proposed. Ref. [68], on the other hand, explored the changes in concentrated solar energy output in Europe due to future climatic changes. It observed an increase of 10% year on year. The financial losses obtained in this study (Tables 1, 3 and 4) instead focus on the raw losses that the solar parks can expect to face before levelling the electricity supply prices and propagating the losses to the consumers. Additionally, similar to the approach presented in this paper, ref. [69] presented a detailed analysis on decision making based on LCOE, efficiency and equivalent CO₂ emissions released.

Table 3. Dust storm event analysis at Benban Solar Park.

Date	Production with Aerosol ¹	Production Without Aerosol ¹	Energy Loss ¹	Extra Energy Loss ¹	Revenue Loss	Equivalent CO ₂ Emissions ²
15/03/2024	7.534	11.248	3.714	-	-	-
16/03/2024	4.763	8.198	3.435	-	-	-
17/03/2024	8.372	12.782	4.410	0.907	USD 56,587.81	633.9
18/03/2024	3.075	8.528	5.454	1.951	USD 121,714.83	1363.4
19/03/2024	11.143	14.645	3.502	-	-	-
20/03/2024	11.357	14.718	3.361	-	-	-

¹ Uni—GWh ² Unit—tonne.

Table 4. Dust storm event analysis at Al Dhafrah Solar Park.

Date	Production with Aerosol ¹	Production Without Aerosol ¹	Energy Loss ¹	Extra Energy Loss ¹	Revenue Loss	Equivalent CO ₂ Emissions ²
22/05/2022	12.788	17.118	4.330	-	-	-
23/05/2022	13.049	17.130	4.081	-	-	-
24/05/2022	12.558	17.142	4.584	-	-	-
25/05/2022	11.692	17.153	5.461	1.141	USD 15,066.76	797.9
26/05/2022	11.220	17.163	5.942	1.62	USD 21,426.02	1134.6
27/05/2022	11.713	17.172	5.460	1.140	USD 15,052.97	797.1
28/05/2022	12.010	17.181	5.172	0.853	USD 11,253.13	595.9
29/05/2022	11.719	17.190	5.471	1.152	USD 15,204.58	805.2
30/05/2022	12.916	17.198	4.282	-	-	-

¹ Unit—GWh. ² Unit—tonne.

4. Conclusions

This study examines the impact of climatological factors, aerosols and clouds, on solar energy production at two of the world's largest solar parks, Benban and Al Dhafrah Solar Parks. The impact of both factors was first quantified into aerosol and cloud effects, respectively, and a trend analysis of both effects over the past 20 years was performed. The trends were quantified into trends of energy production, equivalent emissions released and projected revenue. It was evidently found that aerosol imparts greater impact on production for both locations considering their geographical locations.

The aerosol effect trend observed was a largely falling trend for both locations, -17.78 Wh/m²/year for Benban and -44.88 Wh/m²/year for Al Dhafrah. The cloud effect trend observed was also a similarly falling trend, -36.29 Wh/m²/year at Benban and -70.27 Wh/m²/year at Al Dhafrah. As a result, both solar parks were foreseen to experience increases in annual energy production of 1 GWh/year for Benban and over 1.65 GWh/year for Al Dhafrah. Following this projected increase in energy production, the additional solar energy would mitigate nearly 705.2 tonne/year (Benban) and 1153.7 tonne/year (Al Dhafrah) of equivalent CO₂ emissions and result in revenue boosts of over USD 62,000/year (Benban) and USD 100,000/year (Al Dhafrah). Quantifications of severe dust storm events showed realised losses of 2.86 GWh for Benban and 5.91 GWh for Al Dhafrah, equivalent to 1997.3 tonnes and 4130.6 tonnes of CO₂ emissions, respectively.

Thus, this paper aims to assist decision makers in planning new solar parks by demonstrating a quantification process that assesses the long-term impact of climatic factors by using Earth observation data. The findings provide a new perspective on solar energy planning and management. By showcasing results from two of the world's largest solar parks, the study highlights the practical benefits of Earth observation technology for solar energy planning amid climate change challenges. Furthermore, the proposed methodology can be scaled to broader areas and integrated into decision-making processes, enhancing support for solar energy planning and management.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, P.K. and H.D.; methodology, P.K. and H.D.; software, A.M.; validation, P.K. and Y.K.; formal analysis, H.D.; investigation, P.K. and H.D.; resources, Y.K.; data curation, A.M., H.E.-A. and O.E.; writing—original draft preparation, H.D.; writing—review and editing, P.K. and Y.K.; visualization, H.D.; supervision, P.K. and Y.K.; project administration, P.K.; funding acquisition, P.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Data Availability Statement: All data used in this study can be requested from the corresponding author. All Earth observation data are accessible at the respective official websites.

Acknowledgments: The authors acknowledge the EU-funded CiROCCO project under grant agreement No. 101086497.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AOD	Aerosol Optical Depth
AMF	Aerosol Modification Factor
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
GHG	greenhouse gas
GHI	Global Horizontal Irradiance
PV	photovoltaic
PVGIS	Photovoltaic Geographical Information System
SoDa Pro	Solar Radiation and Meteorological Data Services
UAE	United Arab Emirates

References

- Juruš, P.; Eben, K.; Resler, J.; Krč, P.; Kasanický, I.; Pelikán, E.; Brabec, M.; Hošek, J. Estimating climatological variability of solar energy production. *Sol. Energy* **2013**, *98*, 255–264. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Oka, K.; Mizutani, W.; Ashina, S. Climate change impacts on potential solar energy production: A study case in Fukushima, Japan. *Renew. Energy* **2020**, *153*, 249–260. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Penmetsa, V.; Holbert, K.E. Climate change effects on solar, wind and hydro power generation. In Proceedings of the 2019 North American Power Symposium (NAPS), Wichita, KS, USA, 13–15 October 2019; pp. 1–6.
- Rathod, A.P.S.; Mittal, P.; Kumar, B. Analysis of factors affecting the solar radiation received by any region. In Proceedings of the 2016 International Conference on Emerging Trends in Communication Technologies (ETCT), Dehradun, India, 18–19 November 2016; pp. 1–4.
- Francis, D.; Chaboureaud, J.P.; Nelli, N.; Cuesta, J.; Alshamsi, N.; Temimi, M.; Pauluis, O.; Xue, L. Summertime dust storms over the Arabian Peninsula and impacts on radiation, circulation, cloud development and rain. *Atmos. Res.* **2021**, *250*, 105364.
- Alhebsi, K. Investigating Climate Change, Extreme Weather, Dust Storm, and Solar Energy Nexus over the United Arab Emirates. Ph.D. Thesis, George Mason University, Fairfax, VA, USA, 2023.
- Abuelgasim, A.; Farahat, A. Effect of dust loadings, meteorological conditions, and local emissions on aerosol mixing and loading variability over highly urbanized semiarid countries: United Arab Emirates case study. *J. Atmos. Sol. Terr. Phys.* **2020**, *199*, 105215.
- Gherboudj, I.; Ghedira, H. Assessment of solar energy potential over the United Arab Emirates using remote sensing and weather forecast data. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2016**, *55*, 1210–1224.

9. Beegum, S.N.; Romdhane, H.B.; Ali, M.T.; Armstrong, P.; Ghedira, H. Optical and radiative properties of aerosols over Abu Dhabi in the United Arab Emirates. *J. Earth Syst. Sci.* **2016**, *125*, 1579–1602. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Basha, G.; Phanikumar, D.V.; Kumar, K.N.; Ouarda, T.B.; Marpu, P.R. Investigation of aerosol optical, physical, and radiative characteristics of a severe dust storm observed over UAE. *Remote Sens. Environ.* **2015**, *169*, 404–417.
11. El Chaar, L.; Lamont, L.A. Global solar radiation: Multiple on-site assessments in Abu Dhabi, UAE. *Renew. Energy* **2010**, *35*, 1596–1601.
12. Kosmopoulos, P.G.; Kazadzis, S.; El-Askary, H.; Taylor, M.; Gkikas, A.; Proestakis, E.; Kontoes, C.; El-Khayat, M.M. Earth-observation-based estimation and forecasting of particulate matter impact on solar energy in Egypt. *Remote Sens.* **2018**, *10*, 1870. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. El-Metwally, M.; Alfaro, S.; Wahab, M.A.; Favez, O.; Mohamed, Z.; Chatenet, B. Aerosol properties and associated radiative effects over Cairo (Egypt). *Atmos. Res.* **2011**, *99*, 263–276.
14. Khalil, S.A.; Shaffie, A. Attenuation of the solar energy by aerosol particles: A review and case study. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2016**, *54*, 363–375. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Kumar, K.N.; Suzuki, K. Assessment of seasonal cloud properties in the United Arab Emirates and adjoining regions from geostationary satellite data. *Remote Sens. Environ.* **2019**, *228*, 90–104. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. El-Askary, H.; Kafatos, M. Dust storm and black cloud influence on aerosol optical properties over Cairo and the Greater Delta region, Egypt. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* **2008**, *29*, 7199–7211. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Hou, Y.T. *Cloud-Radiation-Dynamics Interaction*; University of Maryland: College Park, MD, USA, 1990.
18. Tinsley, B.A.; Heelis, R.A. Correlations of atmospheric dynamics with solar activity evidence for a connection via the solar wind, atmospheric electricity, and cloud microphysics. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* **1993**, *98*, 10375–10384. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Welch, R.M.; Cox, S.K.; Davis, J.M. *Solar Radiation and Clouds*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 1980; Volume 17.
20. Fouquart, Y.; Buriez, J.; Herman, M.; Kandel, R. The influence of clouds on radiation: A climate-modeling perspective. *Rev. Geophys.* **1990**, *28*, 145–166. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Nelli, N.; Fissehay, S.; Francis, D.; Fonseca, R.; Temimi, M.; Weston, M.; Abida, R.; Nesterov, O. Characteristics of atmospheric aerosols over the UAE inferred from CALIPSO and sun photometer aerosol optical depth. *Earth Space Sci.* **2021**, *8*, e2020EA001360. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Shokr, M.; El-Tahan, M.; Ibrahim, A.; Steiner, A.; Gad, N. Long-term, high-resolution survey of atmospheric aerosols over Egypt with NASA's MODIS data. *Remote Sens.* **2017**, *9*, 1027. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Elshora, M.; Fayez, E. Characterization of the major aerosol species over Egypt based on 10 years of CAMS reanalysis data. *Atmos. Pollut. Res.* **2024**, *15*, 102094. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Marey, H.; Gille, J.; El-Askary, H.; Shalaby, E.; El-Raey, M. Aerosol climatology over Nile Delta based on MODIS, MISR and OMI satellite data. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **2011**, *11*, 10637–10648. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Kesti, J.; Backman, J.; O'Connor, E.J.; Hirsikko, A.; Asmi, E.; Aurela, M.; Makkonen, U.; Filioglou, M.; Komppula, M.; Korhonen, H.; et al. Aerosol particle characteristics measured in the United Arab Emirates and their response to mixing in the boundary layer. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **2022**, *22*, 481–503. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Hernandez, R.R.; Easter, S.; Murphy-Mariscal, M.L.; Maestre, F.T.; Tavassoli, M.; Allen, E.B.; Barrows, C.W.; Belnap, J.; Ochoa-Hueso, R.; Ravi, S.; et al. Environmental impacts of utility-scale solar energy. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2014**, *29*, 766–779. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Tawalbeh, M.; Al-Othman, A.; Kafiah, F.; Abdelsalam, E.; Almomani, F.; Alkasrawi, M. Environmental impacts of solar photovoltaic systems: A critical review of recent progress and future outlook. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2021**, *759*, 143528. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
28. Guo, X.; Dong, Y.; Ren, D. CO₂ emission reduction effect of photovoltaic industry through 2060 in China. *Energy* **2023**, *269*, 126692. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Jäger-Waldau, A.; Kougias, I.; Taylor, N.; Thiel, C. How photovoltaics can contribute to GHG emission reductions of 55% in the EU by 2030. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2020**, *126*, 109836. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Demirhan, H. Solar Photovoltaic Utilization in Electricity Generation to Tackle Climate Change. *J. Environ. Inform.* **2022**, *40*. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Krauter, S.; Rütther, R. Considerations for the calculation of greenhouse gas reduction by photovoltaic solar energy. *Renew. Energy* **2004**, *29*, 345–355. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Breyer, C.; Koskinen, O.; Blechinger, P. Profitable climate change mitigation: The case of greenhouse gas emission reduction benefits enabled by solar photovoltaic systems. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2015**, *49*, 610–628. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Kavlak, G.; McNerney, J.; Trancik, J.E. Evaluating the causes of cost reduction in photovoltaic modules. *Energy Policy* **2018**, *123*, 700–710. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Li, Z. Prospects of photovoltaic technology. *Engineering* **2023**, *21*, 28–31. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Kabir, E.; Kumar, P.; Kumar, S.; Adelodun, A.A.; Kim, K.H. Solar energy: Potential and future prospects. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2018**, *82*, 894–900. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Verlinden, P. Future challenges for photovoltaic manufacturing at the terawatt level. *J. Renew. Sustain. Energy* **2020**, *12*, 053505. [[CrossRef](#)]

37. Sarver, T.; Al-Qaraghuli, A.; Kazmerski, L.L. A comprehensive review of the impact of dust on the use of solar energy: History, investigations, results, literature, and mitigation approaches. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2013**, *22*, 698–733. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Kumler, A.; Kravitz, B.; Draxl, C.; Vimmerstedt, L.; Benton, B.; Lundquist, J.K.; Martin, M.; Buck, H.J.; Wang, H.; Lennard, C.; et al. Potential effects of climate change and solar radiation modification on renewable energy resources. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2025**, *207*, 114934. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. Solanki, S.K.; Krivova, N.A.; Haigh, J.D. Solar irradiance variability and climate. *Annu. Rev. Astron. Astrophys.* **2013**, *51*, 311–351. [[CrossRef](#)]
40. Jathar, L.D.; Ganesan, S.; Awasarmol, U.; Nikam, K.; Shahapurkar, K.; Soudagar, M.E.M.; Fayaz, H.; El-Shafay, A.; Kalam, M.; Bouadila, S.; et al. Comprehensive review of environmental factors influencing the performance of photovoltaic panels: Concern over emissions at various phases throughout the lifecycle. *Environ. Pollut.* **2023**, *326*, 121474. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Mussard, M.; Amara, M. Performance of solar photovoltaic modules under arid climatic conditions: A review. *Sol. Energy* **2018**, *174*, 409–421. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Zakari, Y.; Vuille, F.; Lehning, M. Climate change impact assessment for future wind and solar energy installations in India. *Front. Energy Res.* **2022**, *10*, 859321. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. Mustafa, R.J.; Gomaa, M.R.; Al-Dhaifallah, M.; Rezk, H. Environmental impacts on the performance of solar photovoltaic systems. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 608. [[CrossRef](#)]
44. Wati, E.; Meukam, P. Impact of the climate change on the site suitability for solar farms: Case study of Cameroon. *Renew. Energy* **2024**, *225*, 120310. [[CrossRef](#)]
45. Fröhlich, C.; Lean, J. Solar irradiance variability and climate. *Astron. Nachrichten* **2002**, *323*, 203–212. [[CrossRef](#)]
46. Gandoman, F.H.; Aleem, S.H.A.; Omar, N.; Ahmadi, A.; Alenezi, F.Q. Short-term solar power forecasting considering cloud coverage and ambient temperature variation effects. *Renew. Energy* **2018**, *123*, 793–805. [[CrossRef](#)]
47. Khataei Maragheh, H. Effect of environmental factors on Solar-panel Power Loss and Photovoltaic Performance. *Geotech. Geol.* **2018**, *14*, 229–233.
48. de Oliveira Azevedo, R.; Rotela Junior, P.; Rocha, L.C.S.; Chicco, G.; Aquila, G.; Peruchi, R.S. Identification and analysis of impact factors on the economic feasibility of photovoltaic energy investments. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 7173. [[CrossRef](#)]
49. Javed, W.; Guo, B.; Figgis, B.; Pomares, L.M.; Aïssa, B. Multi-year field assessment of seasonal variability of photovoltaic soiling and environmental factors in a desert environment. *Sol. Energy* **2020**, *211*, 1392–1402. [[CrossRef](#)]
50. Singh, V.P.; Arya, S.K.; Shankar, A. Analysis of environmental factors affecting the performance of PV solar modules at Hisar. *AIP Conf. Proc.* **2024**, *2900*, 020018.
51. Navothna, B.; Thotakura, S. Analysis on large-scale solar PV plant energy performance–loss–degradation in coastal climates of India. *Front. Energy Res.* **2022**, *10*, 857948. [[CrossRef](#)]
52. Zakari, Y. *Addressing Impact of Climate Change on Wind and Solar Energy Infrastructures: The Case of India*; Technical Report; EPFL: Lausanne, Switzerland, 2022.
53. Jackson, N.D.; Gunda, T. Evaluation of extreme weather impacts on utility-scale photovoltaic plant performance in the United States. *Appl. Energy* **2021**, *302*, 117508. [[CrossRef](#)]
54. Ouria, M. Solar energy potential according to climatic and geometrical parameters of cities and buildings: A case-study from Tabriz City-Iran. *Urban Clim.* **2019**, *28*, 100469. [[CrossRef](#)]
55. Gottschalg, R.; Betts, T.; Williams, S.; Sauter, D.; Infield, D.; Kearney, M. A critical appraisal of the factors affecting energy production from amorphous silicon photovoltaic arrays in a maritime climate. *Sol. Energy* **2004**, *77*, 909–916. [[CrossRef](#)]
56. Mani, M.; Pillai, R. Impact of dust on solar photovoltaic (PV) performance: Research status, challenges and recommendations. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2010**, *14*, 3124–3131. [[CrossRef](#)]
57. Rathod, A.P.S.; Gowri, R.; Dubey, V.P.; Adhikari, A. Factors Affecting the Efficiency of Solar Harnessing Systems: A Brief Review. In Proceedings of the 2024 International Conference on Automation and Computation (AUTOCOM), Dehradun, India, 14–16 March 2024; pp. 684–688.
58. Wang, W.; Shi, H.; Fu, D.; Liu, M.; Li, J.; Shan, Y.; Hong, T.; Yang, D.; Xia, X. Moving beyond the Aerosol Climatology of WRF-Solar: A Case Study over the North China Plain. *Weather Forecast.* **2024**, *39*, 765–780. [[CrossRef](#)]
59. Kosmopoulos, P.; Dhake, H.; Melita, N.; Tagarakis, K.; Georgakis, A.; Stefan, A.; Vaggelis, O.; Korre, V.; Kashyap, Y. Multi-Layer Cloud Motion Vector Forecasting for Solar Energy Applications. *Appl. Energy* **2024**, *353*, 122144. [[CrossRef](#)]
60. Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (Pvgis). Available online: <https://pvgis.com/> (accessed on 9 November 2024).
61. Solar Radiation Data Pro (SoDa Pro). Available online: <https://www.tsv.soda-pro.com/soda-products> (accessed on 9 November 2024).
62. Gueymard, C.A. Impact of on-site atmospheric water vapor estimation methods on the accuracy of local solar irradiance predictions. *Sol. Energy* **2014**, *101*, 74–82. [[CrossRef](#)]
63. Shi, H.; Zhang, J.; Zhao, B.; Xia, X.; Hu, B.; Chen, H.; Wei, J.; Liu, M.; Bian, Y.; Fu, D.; et al. Surface brightening in eastern and central China since the implementation of the Clean Air Action in 2013: Causes and implications. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **2021**, *48*, e2020GL091105. [[CrossRef](#)]
64. Agency, U.S.E.P. Greenhouse Gas Equivalencies Calculator. 2024. Available online: <https://www.epa.gov/energy/greenhouse-gas-equivalencies-calculator> (accessed on 10 August 2024).

65. Mohamed, A.; Maghrabie, H.M. Techno-economic feasibility analysis of Benban solar Park. *Alex. Eng. J.* **2022**, *61*, 12593–12607. [[CrossRef](#)]
66. Hameed, M.A.; Daßler, D.; Alias, Q.M.; Scheer, R.; Gottschalg, R. Economic Consequences Based on Reversible and Irreversible Degradation of PV Park in the Harsh Climate Conditions of Iraq. *Energies* **2024**, *17*, 2652. [[CrossRef](#)]
67. Flowers, M.E.; Smith, M.K.; Parsekian, A.W.; Boyuk, D.S.; McGrath, J.K.; Yates, L. Climate impacts on the cost of solar energy. *Energy Policy* **2016**, *94*, 264–273. [[CrossRef](#)]
68. Crook, J.A.; Jones, L.A.; Forster, P.M.; Crook, R. Climate change impacts on future photovoltaic and concentrated solar power energy output. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2011**, *4*, 3101–3109. [[CrossRef](#)]
69. Hansen, K. Decision-making based on energy costs: Comparing levelized cost of energy and energy system costs. *Energy Strategy Rev.* **2019**, *24*, 68–82. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.